

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MENTAL AND SPIRITUAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN

Akhunov U.R.

Acting Professor of Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) on
Pedagogical Sciences

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***Abstract.** This article discusses the role of physical education and the processes of its implementation in the development of the younger generation, which is the future of our country, into mentally and spiritually perfect people.*

***Keywords:** personality, education, quality, stage, maturity, health.*

INTRODUCTION

The prosperity of independent Uzbekistan, its rise to the level of a great country in economic and social terms depends not only on the intelligence, knowledge and skills of the young generation of hard-working citizens, but also on their health and physical fitness. A positive solution to the fate of the current era and its prospects requires from every citizen, regardless of the field of activity, such human qualities as enthusiasm, enterprise, determination and swiftness. These physical qualities are based on the qualities of strength, speed, flexibility, agility and endurance. Of course, active, purposeful formation of these qualities does not happen by itself, but is carried out through regular and planned participation in sports or physical education in the process of human development.

In our country, raising children and adolescents physically healthy is becoming the main content of the state program. Because the fate of future generations depends on the spiritual and physical fitness of our healthy people today. Our first president I.A. Karimov in his book "High spirituality is an invincible force" noted that "The development of any nation, its place, position and glory in world history directly depend on the mental and physical maturity of its children." A country that cares about the maturity, culture and spirituality of its children, their education, will have a great future.

In this regard, the issues of strengthening the physical and mental health of the younger generation, improving the health of young people in our country have been raised to the level of state policy, a wide range of measures have been taken to ensure a healthy lifestyle and strengthen the love of sports among young people.

It is known that among the material and spiritual types of culture, physical culture is an extremely diverse phenomenon and has always occupied an important place in people's lives. Physical culture is one of the oldest activities of the individual and society, the basis of common culture, its unifying link. From history we know that our ancestors paid special attention to the issue of a spiritually rich, physically healthy and perfect person. They say that the greatest quality of perfection is the perfection of the human body. It was believed that such positive qualities as honesty, abstinence, discipline, contentment, knowledge, patience, conscientiousness, truthfulness, exemplary character, chastity, understanding, intelligence, obedience, forgiveness,

love for the Motherland, strength of spirit, can be achieved only through a healthy body and good health.

The great medical scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina also paid serious attention to the health of the generation, saying: “If a person is strong, healthy and free from all types of genetic diseases, his offspring will be healthy.” Amir Timur continues this tradition in our spiritual values. “I concentrated on finding a bride because I was concerned about marrying my sons, grandsons and relatives. I equated these tasks with state duties: I inquired about her pedigree, seven generations. I learned about their health through my people. If the future bride is free from all defects in her pedigree, manners, health and strength, I have given the country a wedding spectacle and made her a bride”. Also, the commander Amir Timur paid attention to intellectual, moral and physical qualities when hiring ministers, palace servants and soldiers. Persons with any symptoms of disease or who had previously suffered from any infectious diseases were not called up for service, the structural potential of military operations consisted of completely healthy people who were under constant medical examination. In accordance with the military principle applicable to this procedure, we read this requirement in the work “Laws of Timur” of Amir Timur. That is: “Whatever class the noble and courageous soldier may be, give him a place and train him for service and labor.”

In fact, the Great Commander constantly used this training to gather a large number of strong army and healthy soldiers who kept the peace in the country. This educational political system has become a policy of national importance.

Physical education and sports are the basis of physical and mental health. Sufficient physical development creates conditions for normal mental development. The difference between physical work and mental work is that in one the brain plays the main role, and in the other the muscles perform tasks by controlling the brain. As one of the founders of physical knowledge P.F. Lestgaft noted, mental and physical development are inextricably linked. The growth and development of the mind, in turn, requires physical development.

The place and role of physical education in the development of mental and moral education of school-age children can be expressed in two stages:

Stage 1. Children aged 6-11 years – this period is the period when the child first comes to school and masters new conditions. In this case, the growth process of the child's body is not very noticeable, but changes in other indicators prevail, the functions of the organs and systems of the body reach the norm. He/She will now be inclined to perform the tasks of spiritual education and moral rules at a high level. The fact that excitation still prevails over inhibition in the child's central nervous system indicates that he needs a high level of activity. This period is considered a special bridge between childhood and adolescence.

If a child is not active in movement for a long time, then muscle tension increases, attention weakens, and he quickly gets tired. The child is often distracted during lessons and becomes restless. For this reason, it is advisable to conduct morning physical education before the lesson, as well as a minute of physical education in the middle of the lesson.

Stage 2. Children aged 11-15 years – during this period, the processes of excitation and inhibition in the child's central nervous system are gradually balanced, the mobility of nervous processes improves, which affects the child's behavior. He/She will no longer pay much attention to things that excite him, make him happy or upset, he/she will easily engage in mental work instead of playing games and watching.

At this stage, reaching a new level of self-awareness is considered one of the greatest achievements of mental development, the child develops a sense of self-worth. This important process ensures that children will show their unique worldview and personality, and then determine their position. During this period, regular physical exercises of the child affect the development of self-confidence and form his endurance.

From the above, we know that when organizing physical education classes, it is necessary to take into account the level of physical development of adolescents.

In conclusion, it can be noted that from the first days of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main goal was to create a free and prosperous Motherland, a free and prosperous life based on our national spirituality, which occupies an important place in world development. In achieving this great goal, the main attention is paid to the education of the young generation as comprehensively developed, mentally and physically healthy, highly qualified specialists, which is a unique expression of our national traditions and mentality. The national model of personnel training, consistently implemented in our republic, has today received recognition throughout the world and is showing its first results.

However, along with the noted achievements, there are areas that do not fully serve the further development of the physical education system. In particular, the formation of students' knowledge and skills in physical education during the lesson, the organization of classes based on new pedagogical technologies, systematicity and purposefulness are not sufficiently reflected.

In the pedagogical and psychological literature that we have studied, it has been noted that mental and moral education is given special significance in the development of a person as an individual. But although physical education appears in our eyes to be on the second level, it is recognized that neither mental nor moral education can be perfect without physical education, or more precisely, without the influence of physical education.

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